

food assimilation of *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* (Guenée) and *Marasmia patnalis* Bradley (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae) on 12 selected weed plants collected from ricefields and multiplied in the greenhouse.

The weed plants were *Brachiaria mutica*, *Digitaria ciliaris*, *Dactyloctenium aegyptium*, *Echinochloa glabrescens*, *E. crus-galli*, *E. colona*, *Eleusine indica*, *Leptochloa chinensis*, *Leersia hexandra*, *Paspalum distichum*, *Panicum repens*, and *Paspalum conjugatum*.

Third-instar larvae were starved but water satiated for 2 h and weighed individually (W_1). Leafcuts of weed plant, susceptible IR36, or resistant TKM6 rice (30- to 35-d-old) were offered in a no-choice test to individual LF larvae for 24 h. Larval weight (W_2) was recorded 2 h after the end of the feeding period. The setup was replicated 10 times.

Leaf area consumed was measured using a leaf area meter. Food assimilation was computed:

$$\text{Food assimilation} = W_1 \left(\frac{C_1 - C_2}{C_1} \right) + (W_2 - W_1)$$

where W_1 and W_2 are initial and final weights of test insects and C_1 and C_2 initial and final weights of control insects.

C. medinalis larvae fed most on *D. ciliaris*, followed by *E. glabrescens*, *P. conjugatum*, and *E. indica* (see figure). Feeding on susceptible IR36 was lower than on *D. ciliaris* but comparable to feeding on TKM6, *E. colona*, *E. crus-galli*, *L. chinensis*, *L. hexandra*, and *P. distichum*. Feeding on *B. mutica* and *P. repens* was significantly lower than on either rice varieties as well as on most of the weeds tested.

Food assimilation by *C. medinalis* was highest on *P. conjugatum*, followed by *E. glabrescens*, *D. ciliaris*, *D. aegyptium*, and *L. hexandra*. Food assimilation on *E. indica*, *E. crus-galli*, *P. distichum*, and *E. colona* was similar to that on both susceptible IR36 and resistant TKM6. Food assimilation on *P. repens* was significantly lower than on the rice varieties and most of the weeds tested.

M. patnalis larvae fed most on susceptible IR36 and resistant TKM6. Feeding on *L. hexandra* and *L. chinensis* was comparable to feeding on IR36. Feeding on

Leaf area consumption and food assimilation by third-instar larvae of *C. medinalis* and *M. patnalis* on graminaceous weed plants and rice hosts.

the other weed plants tested was significantly lower.

Food assimilation by *M. patnalis* larvae was highest on the two rice varie-

ties and significantly lower on *L. hexandra* and *L. chinensis*. There was either very low or no food assimilation on the other weeds. ■

Mass rearing of a mirid predator

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Mirid predator *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis* Reuter can be mass-reared on brown planthopper (BPH) eggs, using TN1 rice plants.

Adult mirids collected in the field are introduced into mylar cages containing

several 30-d-old TN1 rice plants infested with five gravid BPH females (see figure). Plants, mirids, and BPH females are transferred into the oviposition cage. Plants are transferred to emerging cage after 24 h. The door and top of the 45- × 55- × 60-cm cage are made of glass; the three other sides, of fine nylon mesh.

When the mirid eggs hatch, some gravid BPH females are added to provide food for the mirids. Each cage will produce mirids of known age, which can be used for experiments. ■

Procedure for mass-rearing *C. lividipennis*. DAI = days after mirid introduction.